

Appraisal Patterns of Emotions in User-Product Interaction

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Abstract

Appraisal theorists assert that emotional experiences always involve quick evaluation processes, i.e. appraisals. They believe that those evaluation processes play a causal role in the elicitation of emotions. That is to say, activating an appraisal will result in the corresponding emotion. From this perspective, designing for emotional experiences can benefit from understanding appraisal models. However, the appraisal components, as discussed in appraisal literature, are too general and vague to be directly used by designers. This study aimed at specifying these general components, as well as providing an initial discussion about the appraisal patterns of some emotions elicited in user-product interaction. To this end, a study composed of an experience sampling phase and an in-depth interview phase was designed (N=29). The results implied that motive consistency is the main appraisal component underlying various emotional experiences in interaction with products. This component is specified in terms of different levels of user motives. In addition, the appraisal patterns of happiness/joy, contentment/satisfaction, and anger/irritation were discussed.

Conference theme: Design and emotion: Theoretical issues or Usage & Interaction

Keywords: Appraisal components, User-Product Interaction, happiness/joy, contentment/satisfaction, anger/irritation

Introduction

Designing products to evoke certain emotions, i.e. emotional design, can be facilitated by an understanding of emotional processes. In emotion psychology, it is believed that an emotion always involves an evaluation of the situation with respect to an individual's personal concerns, i.e. an appraisal (Frijda, 1986; Lazarus, 1991). Appraisal theories state that experiencing an unpleasant emotion requires appraising a situation as harmful to personal well-being, whereas a pleasant emotion involves appraising a situation as beneficial. As a specific example, consider a person who is trying to finish writing a document before a tight deadline. In such a rush, if the word processor that the person uses does not respond, the person would most probably get angry. The experience of anger in this case, according to appraisal theorists, involves the individual's evaluation of the word processor as blocking his/her goal of finishing the document in time.

In literature, several different appraisal components have been proposed. These components differ from each other in terms of the aspect of the situation that is focused. For instance, the motive consistency component is basically about whether the confronted situation is beneficial or harmful to one's well being. The agency component is about who or what caused the evocative situation (Roseman, 2001). Combinations of different appraisal components result in different emotions and each emotion has a unique pattern of appraisal components. For instance, anger involves appraising the situation as harmful and caused by an outside agent. In order for the same situation to evoke guilt, for instance, it must be appraised as harmful, but caused by one's self (Roseman, 2001).

According to several appraisal theorists, appraisals have a causal role in the elicitation of an emotion (Roseman & Evdokas, 2004, Kappas, 2006). That is to say, activation of a particular appraisal pattern results in the corresponding emotion. From this perspective, understanding and designing for appraisals seems to be a promising approach to emotional design. In the design literature, several models and frameworks have been proposed (Jordan, 1999, Norman 2002). These previous works have identified several sources of emotions in human-product interaction, such as emotions due to social interactions or emotions due to sensorial experiences. These sources are very helpful to evaluate the emotional impact of existing products, however, their help for concept generation is limited. In contrast, the appraisal

approach, as illustrated by Desmet (2002), is a promising way for generating product concepts that aim to evoke some specific emotions. The basic problem with using appraisal information for emotional design is that the appraisal components proposed in literature are too general. For instance, it is not clear what motive consistency actually means in a particular user-product interaction episode and what type of motives users may have. An additional complicating factor is that there is not a consensus about the involvement of some particular components for some emotions. This paper focuses on these two problems. The goal is to find out if the appraisal components that are proposed in the psychology domain can also be traced in emotional experiences with products, and to provide a detailed account of those components that are identified. To attain that goal, a three-phase explorative study was designed. The basis of the study was an experience sampling study in which participants were asked to report their emotional experiences with products, whenever they were invited by an SMS. In total 170 emotion records were collected. These reports were elaborated in a subsequent in-depth interview stage. The diary reports and the decoded interview accounts were then analyzed for the involved appraisal components. Due to the limited space, only the most frequently reported emotions are discussed in this paper: happiness/joy, contentment/satisfaction and anger/irritation.

Main appraisal components and appraisal patterns of emotions

In literature, as mentioned, several appraisal components have been proposed by various authors. Despite the nuances in the definitions and characterizations of these components, 6 main appraisal components can be identified: motive consistency, expectation confirmation, agency, standard conformance, coping potential, and certainty.

Appraisal components

a. Motive consistency component

The basis of most emotions is the evaluation of a situation's significance in relation to an individual's goals and needs, i.e. motives. A situation may evoke a pleasant emotion if it is appraised as an attainment of a goal or an improvement to the way to attain a goal, i.e. highly consistent with one's motives. For example, a dress may help someone to look more beautiful and feel special, and therefore happy. In contrast, if one appraises a situation as blocking the attainment of goals, i.e. high motive inconsistency, a negative emotion is elicited (Frijda, 1986, Lazarus, 1991).

A similar appraisal component is the intrinsic pleasantness component proposed by Scherer (2001). As the name implies, it is about the pleasantness of a stimulus, such as the sweetness of a candy bar. Scherer (2001) claims that a pleasantness appraisal does not involve any relation to personal motives. However, as Moors, De Houwer & Eelen (2004) put it nicely, “It indeed seems difficult, if not impossible, to find an example of intrinsic valence that is not related in some way to motivation, for even the simplest examples of valence may relate to a hedonic concern.”(Moors et al. 2004, p.30). Other authors support the relation between motives and sensorial pleasure. For instance, Johnston (2003) states that sensorial pleasures, such as the pleasantness in response to sweet food or curved and smooth lines, is basically a functional inheritance from our ancestors, due to the benefits these had to the basic motive of survival (see also Hekkert & Leder, 2008, for the by-product hypothesis of sensorial pleasure). Therefore in this study, the pleasantness appraisal (including the sensorial pleasantness) is considered to be a sub category of the motive consistency appraisal.

b. Expectation confirmation component

One may have explicit expectations about an outcome of an event. The expectation confirmation component is about whether the actual outcome of an event confirms or violates previous expectations (Scherer, 2001). In relation to products, one may have different expectations, varying from an expectation about an unexplored aspect of a product, e.g. performance prior to usage, to the expectations about the consequence of a user action, e.g. pushing a button to enter the menu of a cellular phone. One can get disappointed or satisfied when the outcomes respectively violate or confirm expectations.

c. Agency component

This component is about who or what is responsible for a situation. Some emotional situations involve self agency, such as being proud of succeeding in installing a tent, or being ashamed of wearing a pretentious sweater. Some other emotional situations may be attributed to other agents resulting in emotions such as anger or admiration. Yet some other emotions cannot be attributed to any particular agents and are attributed to circumstances, e.g. being sad for losing a cherished object (Roseman, 2001, Scherer, 2001, Ortony et al., 1988).

d. Standards conformance component

The meaning of the situation with respect to social standards, norms and values is included in different appraisal models (Scherer, 2001, Ortony et al., 1988). A situation can be appraised as violating standards resulting in emotions like anger or shame, or it can be appraised as conforming standards resulting in pride or admiration. One can appraise the delicate details of a hand-made bag as praiseworthy and therefore admire the producer of the handbag.

e. Coping potential component

Coping potential is basically about whether one can change the actual or expected harmful aspects of a situation (Roseman, 2001). One can appraise oneself as powerful enough to influence the situation. For instance, anger involves such an appraisal as manifested by the aggressive behavior associated with it. In contrast, emotions such as fear or anxiety involve low coping potential, meaning that one appraises oneself as having little control or power to change the situation, which results in getting away from the situation. Computer anxiety, in literature, is usually associated with an appraisal of finding oneself powerless to manipulate and control the computer (Busch, 1995).

f. Certainty component:

One may or may not be certain about a situation or the harms or benefits related to a situation. An appraisal of certainty differentiates emotions involving low certainty such as hope and fear from those involving high certainty, e.g. happiness and sadness.

Appraisal patterns of emotions

a. Happiness/joy

Almost all appraisal theorists agree that happiness/joy involves high motive consistency, i.e. a pleasantness or attainment of a goal. However, for the involvement of other components, there is still a debate going on. For instance, Roseman (2001) claims that happiness/joy involves circumstance agency, whereas other authors such as Scherer (2001) or Ortony et al. (1988) do not consider agency as a causal component for happiness/joy. In addition, there are also conflicting views on the involvement of the certainty component (Ellsworth & Smith, 1988, Scherer, 2001).

b. Contentment/satisfaction

Like happiness/joy, contentment/satisfaction involves motive consistency. The other appraisal component that differentiates this emotion from the previous emotion is the involvement of the expectation confirmation component. Ortony et al. (1988) claim that contentment/satisfaction involves a confirmation of an expectation about the desirable outcome.

c. Anger/irritation

Anger/irritation involves high motive inconsistency, blocking goals or delaying the attainment of goals. In addition, most authors agree on the involvement of “other” agency, which can be a person or even an inanimate object (Scherer, 2001). Roseman (2001), referring to the attack tendency in the experience of anger, associates anger with high coping potential. However, there is not a consensus about the role of this component in anger/irritation causation (Smith & Kirby, 2004). Likewise, involvement of the component standard confirmation in anger is debatable. Scherer (2001) includes high standard violation in the appraisal pattern of anger/irritation, while others do not.

The Study

An explorative study in three phases was conducted: a sensitizing phase, a self-report phase, and an interview phase. Participants (N=29) were master students at the Industrial Design Engineering Department of Delft University of Technology, and were paid for their contribution.

In the sensitizing phase, participants reported emotional experiences in their daily lives in a questionnaire. Each participant received a set of 10 emotions that were randomly selected from a list of 33 affective concepts groups developed by Scherer (2005). Participants were asked to report events in which they had experienced these ten emotions. For each report, they were also asked to describe what had happened, and to explain why they experienced the particular emotion.

In the second phase, an adaptation of the experience sampling method (ESM; Hektner, Schmidt & Csikszentmihalyi, 2007) was used to capture participants’ actual emotional experiences with consumer products. ESM was developed as a structured method to collect affective response related information that is subject to memory bias in retrospective

reporting. Participants received a diary booklet and were asked to answer some diary questions whenever they were invited by an SMS. The basic question was to report the last emotion experienced while interacting with a product. To overcome the difficulties in labeling and communicating the emotional experiences, the list used in the first phase was also used in the second phase. Participants either picked one of the listed emotions or reported an additional emotion that was not included in the list. Then, they were asked to report the product that had been involved in the experience, to describe the events that took place and to provide a causal explanation for the emotional activation. The participants were also asked to take a photo of the product that they reported.

The second phase was carried out in two different ways. For the first 19 participants, the study lasted for three days. Each of these participants received one to three SMS's at random moments of the day, summing up to six for the entire study period. The reports of these respondents showed a disproportional high number of cases of irritation and anger. To ensure variability, the remaining participants were asked not to report examples of anger and irritation. Based on the low return rate for the first 19 participants, the signaling schedule was changed to cover ten days and each day only one SMS was sent. The signaling times were randomized over participants and days, in an attempt to cover a variety of different daily activities that may take place throughout the day.

The third step was an interview that was designed to identify the participants' appraisals of the situation. After an explanation of the procedure, participants first read their own reports to recall the experiences. Then the interviewer asked several open-ended questions that aimed to disclose the details of the experience, such as the activity the participant was involved in when experiencing the emotion, the responses of the product, and the presence or absence of other people. During the session, the photographs of the products were shown, which facilitated recalling the experience and communicating about the experience with the interviewer. An average interview session lasted for 45 minutes. All phases of the study were conducted in English.

Results

Appraisal pattern of happiness/joy

Twenty emotional records were collected for happiness/joy. Each of the reports included at least one motive consistency related appraisal comment. In order to specify the motive

consistency component, the motive types and specific motives related to each case were identified and these motives are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The motive types and examples for happiness/joy

Type of motives	Motives	Examples
To experience sensorial pleasantness (8/20)	Visual pleasantness (1/8)	A beautiful nail clipper
	Auditory pleasantness (2/8)	Window blind makes a pleasant sound when it is opened
	Olfactory pleasantness (1/8)	Taking a shower with a shower sponge smelling like watermelon
	Tactual pleasantness (1/8)	Pleasant “bubbly” feeling of an electronic toothbrush
	Gustatory pleasantness (1/8)	Eating a tasty hamburger
	Kinesthetic pleasantness (2/8)	Stapling the documents with a mini-stapler
To attain a general personal goal (16/20)	Social belonging (3/16)	Chatting with family abroad through a web-cam, laptop
	Social interaction (4/16)	Receiving a pleasant SMS
	Physical challenge (2/16)	Playing with hoolahop
	Taking good care of the self (2/16)	Brushing the teeth with an electronic toothbrush
	Intellectual stimulation (2/16)	Magical working mechanism of a coffee percolator
	Being independent and powerful (1/16)	Owning a Jeep
	Feeling familiar and safe (1/16)	Being able to open the lock of a new apartment
Being beautiful (1/16)	The consequences of putting on false eyelashes	
To attain an interaction goal (1/20)	Installation goal	Finishing installing the tent as a marker of the start of a leisure time

In all cases, participants reported external attributions (other or product or circumstances agencies, instead of self agency). The cases involving sensorial pleasantness and most of the general personal goal attainment cases were particularly attributed to particular qualities of products, e.g. “supersonic” quality of an electronic toothbrush. Cases of attainment of a social belonging goal were attributed to other people’s agency.

Almost all cases (19/20) involved high levels of certainty of experienced pleasantness or goal attainment. Only one case involved a long-term benefit (i.e. taking good care of teeth), however, this case was also accompanied by a pleasant tactual feeling of the toothbrush.

Appraisal pattern of contentment/satisfaction

A total of 18 reports were collected for contentment/satisfaction. The findings supported the contribution of the motive consistency component. In one case, the contentment was due the pleasantness of a refined design. For each of the remaining cases cases a goal achievement was reported. The type of motives and examples are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: The types of motives and examples for contentment/satisfaction

Type of motives	Motives	Examples	
To attain a general personal goal (1/18)	Intellectual stimulation (1/18)	A tape dispenser with smart material selection and mechanism solution	
To attain a contextualized personal goal (3/18)	Attainment of a consumption goal (2/18)	Drinking the coffee prepared by the coffee maker after a hard day work	
	Attainment of a purchase goal (1/18)	Finding the perfect present for a friend in a search in the market	
To attain an interaction goal (14/18)	Upkeep goal (1/18)	Arranging the songs according to genre in the music player software	
	Preparation goal (1/18)	Finding the remote control, to change the TV channel	
	Usage goal (12/18)	Goal of easy and efficient use (6)	Easy to use bag with proper number of specialized sections
		Goal of having good performance (4)	A hairwax that works just well for the user's type of hair
		Goal of having sensorial pleasures (2)	A drawing paper that feels nice

The basic difference between contentment/satisfaction and happiness/joy is that in contentment/satisfaction cases, most of these goals had been previously expected to be attained (16/18). In 5/18 cases, the expectations were about a reward in return to product usage, or a phase completion in product usage. Drinking coffee after preparing it with a coffee machine, or completing the arrangement of songs according to their genres in a music

player software are examples of that type of situations. In other cases (13/18), the expectations were about the particular usage episode and/or the product qualities that influence those usage episodes.

Appraisal pattern of anger/irritation

28 anger/irritation reports were collected. In all reports (28/28) there was a motive inconsistent aspect that was reported as a cause of the anger/ irritation. The types of obstructed motives and examples are provided in Table 3.

Table 3: The types of motives and examples for anger/irritation

Type of motives	Motives	Examples
To attain a contextualized personal goal (Blocked)(10/28)	Work/study related goals (5)	Missing the class because of turning off the alarm mistakenly
	Social activities related goals (3)	Being late to a party because of not being able to wrap the present properly
	Personal care related goals (1)	Getting awakened by the alarm clock
	Environmental care related goals (1)	Spilling coffee on the table with a flask
To attain an interaction goal (Blocked) (10/28)	Usage goal (10)	A remote control that does not respond A coffee vendor that gives only a half full cup of coffee
To attain an interaction goal (Delayed) (5/28)	Delay of a usage goal (5)	A software that responds very slowly A washing machine tap that waits too long before letting the door open
To avoid sensorial unpleasantness (5/28)	Pain (3)	Cutting hand while trying to open bottle with a corkscrew
	Discomfort (2)	Getting wet in the rain due to the breakdown of an umbrella

As suggested by the literature, in some of the accounts (12/28), the participants reported the encountered situation (mostly frustration, or disturbance) shouldn't have taken place as a basic violation of a norm. Although this basic standard violation seems central, in some other cases (11/28) the participants explicitly mentioned other, more specific standards pointing to some problematic product aspects and refined standards. For instance, a participant stated,

“...this bike light is supposed to be simple, and it should be simple, but I have to put in so much effort to make it work.”

The results of the study indicated that when anger/irritation was directed to the product, an appraisal of product agency was necessary (22/28). However, the study also showed that not every instant of interaction related to anger/irritation was directed towards the product (5/28). For example, a participant reported a case of irritation caused by spilling hot tea on the table while trying to fill a cup. In this account, although the user did not attribute any responsibility to the flask that is used to fill the cup, as the flask of the tap was not fastened tightly, the situation was still irritating. In 2/28 reports, the product had no apparent responsibility in bringing up the motive-inconsistent situation, but the participants still reported an attribution to the product at the time of the experience.

None of the participants in this study explicitly stated a perceived high coping potential in response to the angering situation. None of the respondents explicitly stated that they were in control or they were able to cope with the situation or there was something to do about the motive relevant aspects of the situation, e.g. in an accident during the usage of a corkscrew, the harm was already done and there is nothing to make it undone. In contrast, most of the reports for anger/irritation involved low control or coping appraisals, e.g. not being able to open the drawer or a cap of a water bottle. In our view, this implies that the high control potential is inherent in a typical human-product interaction episode. Although a user cannot undo motive-inconsistent aspects, e.g. hurting oneself with a corkscrew, he/she is still capable of coping with the motive-inconsistent aspects of the product, such as eliminating further problems by getting the product that is not functioning repaired, using the product with more care, or even by replacing the product with another one or a substitute.

Discussion

The results indicated that many of the components that have been reported in the psychology literature could also be identified in the context of user-product interaction. The basic contribution of the study was to specify the motive-consistency component in user-product interaction. The study revealed several levels of user motives. Firstly, products as possessions and tools can be used to attain general personal goals, such as being beautiful with a necklace, being successful with the work carried on a laptop, or being healthier with the help

of a treadmill. The products can also serve as tools in attainment of contextualized goals. The contextualized goals are active, meaning that they are conscious goals. Attainment of these goals marks a progress towards a related general goal. For instance, to be successful in working life (general goal) one must be in the office in time (contextualized condition) in a proper condition (contextualized goal) and one should fulfill her responsibilities in time (contextualized goal), etc. Furthermore, to reach a contextualized goal one usually has to interact with various tools and gadgets. For instance, in a typical working day morning, to be able to be at work in time and in a proper condition, one may need a cup of coffee to get ready for the working day and this calls for an interaction with a coffee machine. The goals inherent in these interactions, such as being able to operate the coffee maker, are called interaction goals. The identified goal typologies may be fitted into a hierarchy as discussed in Ortony et al. (1988). The general goals depend on attainment of several contextualized goals and therefore they are more important than the contextualized goals. The same relation can be seen between the contextualized goals and the interaction goals. The relationship between these goals is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Goal hierarchy in user-product interaction

An issue that remains to be solved by further research is whether there is a relationship between particular goal types and particular emotions. In the light of the discussion of Ortony

et al. (1988) one may expect that attainment or blockage of more important goals would evoke more arousing emotions e.g. joy/happiness instead of contentment/satisfaction. The results of this study confirm such a picture. The happiness/joy situations involved more personal goals than contentment/satisfaction situations do. Furthermore, attainment of usage goals yielded joy/happiness only when the successful usage was unexpected (most probably due to the complexity of usage or the low skills of the user) or when the attainment of usage goals represented attainment of a higher level and more important goals.

In addition to goals, the study also pointed at the role of sensorial experiences (both pleasant and unpleasant) in evoking emotions. For instance, pleasant sensorial experiences, especially when they are unexpected, could result in joy/happiness. In this context, tactile, auditory, and olfactory pleasantness may create intense pleasantness, as the qualities are not perceived at an initial encounter with the products. Visual pleasantness, when experienced in contexts that are not expected, such as for a nail clipper, can also provide joy or happiness.

An event in interaction with a product may affect various user motives at different levels. The relationship between particular motives or particular combinations of motives (even at different levels) and particular emotions is a question to be addressed by future research. In case of such a relationship, designers can focus on these motives or motive levels as a strategy of emotional design, i.e. design for motive consistency. This study has also taken a step forward in identifying the appraisal patterns of some emotions in user-product interaction. In the future, through controlled experiments and tools designed to measure appraisals, the appraisal patterns of emotions in user-product interaction will be further clarified. Design for emotion can then be reformulated as ‘design for appraisal components’ of intended emotions, such as design for standard conformance and design for coping potential.

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